

Pyruvic acid ($\mu\text{g/g}$ fresh wt)

α Ketoglutaric acid ($\mu\text{g/g}$ fresh wt)

Unknown ketoacid ($\mu\text{g/g}$ fresh wt)

Ketoacid content of 2 healthy and infected varieties. Tirupati, India.

Lesser amounts of ketoacids were found in IET4141 than in TN1. The three ketoacids were present in all stages of healthy and inoculated leaves of TN1. But the unknown ketoacid was absent at stage 1 of healthy plants and stages 1 and 2 of inoculated IET4141.

α -ketoglutaric acid was present in higher quantities than the two other ketoacids in both varieties (see figure).

Accumulation of ketoacids in susceptible TN1 shows that the tricarboxylic acid cycle of the plant is affected during disease development.

Pyruvic acid at 500 ppm was phytotoxic to both varieties. α -ketoglutaric acid was not phytotoxic, but that and the unknown ketoacid may contribute indirectly to symptom development. □

For information on ordering IRRI publications, write Communication and Publications Dept., Div. R, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Resistance to bacterial blight (BB) in rice germplasm material

R. N. Singh, A. T. Khan, and B. N. Mahto, N. D. University of Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Dabha Semar, Faizabad, U.P., India

We evaluated part of the rice germplasm collection at the Crop Research Station, Dabha Semar, for reaction to BB pathogen *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye during the 1985 and 1986 wet seasons (1 Jun-30 Nov). Each test entry was planted in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with the suspension of a local isolate at maximum tillering and disease was rated (*Standard evaluation system for rice*) 15 d and 30 d after inoculation. Final scores were used to classify the germplasm.

None of the genotypes was found to be free from infection, and only IET6155 had a disease score of 2 (see table).

Reaction of rice germplasm material to the local isolate of BB pathogen, Faizabad, U. P. India, 1985 and 1986.

Germplasm material	Reaction score ^a	Varieties (no.) with similar score
IET6155	2	1
IET4555, NP085, RP419, Pant Dhan 4, NDU7, NDU22, T63, M23, H62, IET4141	3	10
IET8675, Restonoorin 21-9, T43, W1278, RR51-1, NDR88	4	6
NDR80, NDR84, NDR97, Saket 4, Type 3, CH45, CH1059, HDLL 39, NDU21, NDU37, NDU39, NDU48, SLO-17, SRA41, IET6238, Basmati 370, Pankaj, Ranikazal, Chainphool, Kalakand	5	20
Narendra 1, Narendra 2, NDR308, China 4, Champa coarse, Rohini 1708, K333, CH1039, IET9782, FS18, CR1416, T6, Joginia, FR9, K39, RP79-9, Sorhi, Anandi, CBF, Ramaniya	6	20
IR28, NDR119, Indrasan, Ratna, IR24, Improved Sona, Sarjoo 52, Dehula, Lalsar, Satha Opening, Anjani I, Padhini, T113, T132, Dulhiniya, T102, Agwar, Karhani (B), Garer, Bazarbhog, JBS1241, T128, T124, Bagari, Banshawa, Bilaspur, Carreon, Champa (F), Delha, Dadhaha, Dudiha, FRG4, FRG10, Jaisuria, Jalhar (C) 11, Kanga (Turahwa), KPW6B, Motibadam, Motipandey, MT4, NDR82, Pahuna, Soron, Sonachoor, Sumokhan, Tudat	7	46
Govind, NDR118, Kachni, Karanga, Tinpakhiyal, Dalkachari, Gajraj, Lakand, Bakaiya, Rohan 2662, Rambhog, Velluthacheera, Chinigurdi 11, Sapna, Sawani bhadai, Selection-8, Lalki bhadai, Lalkawa, Katki I, Katki II, Hari Nibbu, Culture 4, T136, Neebbu, Bagari (B), Karhani (R), Bhadai (R), Babu Ram, NDR501, Pusa 33-18, T42, IR30, Ashahaniya, T-86, Kashi, T116, Kulsha, Motafarm, IR8	8	39
Rasi, Pusa 33, Cauvery, Saket 1, Saket 2, Saket 3, Jhona 349, N22, Madhuri, T21, Prasad, Kodaya, Kodya Improved, Culture 4 (RE), Karhan, Aktahwa (Red), Aktahwa (Black), Nootan, Dudhi, Champa fine, Ram Bilas, Bakain, Mungera, Sahdeyia, Rodola, Rohani, Reshma, Rajbhog, IET6663, Harikesh, Bhadai (B), Bhadai (W), Bala, Bakki, Singul, Satha Band (B), Satha Band (W), Parsom, Usha, T1242, T2, T46, KSR142, Bhunali, IET7301, Kota Basmati, T129, Gajgaur (B), Kapoorchini, Sarjoo 49, Anjana, Champa (C), Kalamdan, Mutra, Sukhawan, Talman, Tinpakhiya II, Akatahwa (FD), Gheebhat, Sath fine, Karnya, Kashi P. D., Katri III, Madhukar, NDR-49, Ramkajara, Rohan, Sawani, Akatahwa (T. D.), Anand, Basmati, Bindibali, Bindi kali, FH-109, Gajgaur, Gajgaur II (W), Jaya, Karanji, L. C. Pratapgarh, Madanchand, Mangova, Motifarm, Muskan, Nutex, Pasarhi, Safedawa, Sajna, Shyamghata, Sona, Turhawa, Lalka, T(N) 1.	9	92

^a Standard evaluation system for rice (1980).

Disease selection in rice in Colombia and Central America

F. Cuevas-Perez and J. S. Gaona, IRTTP Latin America, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT), Apartado Aereo No. 6713, Cali, Colombia

Materials are tested by CIAT for disease reaction prior to dispatch to national programs in Central America. Evaluations are done in Villavicencio, Colombia, a highly favorable disease

environment where blast (Bl) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, leaf scald (LSc) by *Gerlachia oryzae*, and brown spot (BS) by *Helminthosporium oryzae* are endemic.

We studied whether selecting under the high-disease environment prevalent in Villavicencio would predict disease performance in Central America, and compared the efficiency of this testing with selecting entries based only on Bl bed readings.

The analysis was based on disease

data reported from CIAT Rice Program evaluation plots in Villavicencio and from IRTTP collaborators in Central America who reported moderate to severe disease levels in 1982-86 for Bl and in 1985-86 for LSc and BS. Data for 1984 were not used because no disease evaluations from Colombia were available that year.

Each line was classified as selected for a given disease when it received a score lower than that of the nearest susceptible check in the field (*Standard evaluation system for rice*). The coincidence in selection between Colombia and Central America was estimated for each disease as the mean probability for a line to be selected in both locations.

The probability of coincidence in selection for Bl was 0.7 for 1982-83, when selection in Colombia was based on data from the uniform Bl bed in Palmira. It increased to 0.92 during 1985-86, when selection was based on field evaluations in Villavicencio. The predictability of selections done in Colombia for Central America for LSc and BS was calculated as 0.80 for 1985-86.

This indicates high similarity of the race distribution of Bl and the disease environment between Villavicencio, Colombia, and testing sites in Central America.

To estimate the consistency across time of disease evaluations done in Colombia, we calculated the probability of coincidence using 1985-86 data from observational nurseries planted in consecutive years in Colombia. Probabilities of coincidence were 0.83 for Bl and 0.93 for LSc (see table). Coincidence for BS could not be estimated because incidence was low in 1986. No significant differences were observed between coincidence values of leaf Bl and LSc within years in Colombia and between Colombia and Central America for the period and genotypes considered.

We estimate that Bl and LSc evaluation in Villavicencio can predict reaction in Central America at least 80% of the time. Consistent BS evaluations might be very difficult to obtain. □